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Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv
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SPECTROSCOPY OF MOLECULES AND CRYSTALS

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of XXVI Galyna Puchkovska International School-Seminar

Dedicated to 90th birthday of Professor Galyna Puchkovska

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Mechanical Spectroscopy of SiO₂, nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polymers

A. Onanko, D. Charnyi, Y. Onanko, O. Dmytrenko, M. Kulish, T. Pinchuk-Rugal, M. Yatsiuk, E. Matselyuk, S. Marysyk, A. Gaponov, L. Kurochka, P. Ilyin

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X I am applying for **Bruker Customer Excellence Award** (see Award Guideline at [icms.intibs.pl](https://www.bruker.com/ics-intibs.pl))

In this work mechanical spectroscopy of SiO₂, radiation and structural functionalized nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MCNT) and polyethylene (C₂H₄)_n, polyvinylchloride (C₂H₃Cl)_n, polyamide (NH(CH₂)₅CO)_n were researched. After stopping of laser radiation action of fusion solidification begun exactly from the surface, but the crater underbody is extended (molten) and created additional squeezing mechanical tension σ_i , that „pull” central part of crater surface [1].

The distribution diagrams of polarization vectors $\vec{U}, \vec{n}$ of quasilongitudinal velocity $V_{\parallel}$ in SiO₂ is presented in Fig. 1. The value of mechanical spectroscopy, internal friction background Q^{-1}_0 after temperature, mechanical treatments describes the changes of the elastic stress σ_i fields in SiO₂, nanocomposite.

Fig. 1 The distribution diagrams of polarization vectors $\vec{U}, \vec{n}$ of quasilongitudinal velocity $V_{\parallel}$ in SiO₂.

The crater fusion depth Δh at constant intensity I and laser irradiation time t is limited by the local heat-conducting and establishment of “time-equilibrium” distribution of temperature gradients ΔT perpendicular to the crater axis and along it.

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- [1] A. P. Onanko, L. V. Kuzmych, Y. A. Onanko et al., *J. Materials Research Express*, **2023**, 10(10), pp. 106511(7), <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2053-1591/acfecc>.